

Original Article

Knowledge, Attitude, and Health-seeking Behaviours of Health Professionals Undergoing Postgraduate Studies at a North-east University of the United Kingdom, towards Blindness Prevention from Glaucoma

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Abstract

Background: Glaucoma is one of the leading causes of visual impairment. It accounts for the leading cause of blindness registration to the National Health Service (NHS) in the United Kingdom (UK). Only half of the total number of people diagnosed with glaucoma in the UK seek treatment, which raises concern about their attitude and health-seeking behaviour. Health professionals have been identified as agents of health behaviour change. Nevertheless, their impact and influence on behaviour change agenda will depend on their knowledge and attitude as well as their eye-health-seeking behaviour toward glaucoma.

Aim: To examine the level of knowledge, attitude, and health-seeking behaviours of health professionals undergoing postgraduate studies at the University of Sunderland towards blindness prevention from glaucoma.

Methods: This study adopted a quantitative approach using a cross-sectional design. After obtaining informed consent, a total of 104 participants were voluntarily surveyed online using a semi-structured questionnaire. Data were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Results: The finding on glaucoma awareness level amongst the respondents was high (79.8%). Knowledge level was fair (44.2%). Most of the respondents did not have a good attitude and eye-health-seeking behaviour toward glaucoma. The age and/or family history of blindness of the respondents had a statistically significant relationship with the awareness, knowledge level, and attitude toward glaucoma.

Conclusion: It would be wrong to assume that all health professionals are fully knowledgeable about glaucoma. Mechanisms to equip health professionals with the right glaucoma information should be prioritized to enable effective engagement in public health education and improvement campaigns on glaucoma towards blindness prevention.

Key words: Glaucoma, Knowledge, Attitude, Health-seeking behaviour, Blindness prevention

Introduction

The public health burden of vision loss has become more profound as the population of the world continues to grow and age. Glaucoma is playing a major role in vision loss and increasing blindness [1]. Visual perception involves a process in which information from visible light can be accurately processed by the brain to recognize our surrounding environment [2]. Visual impairment or blindness can result when the anatomical and visual pathway that leads to the brain is distorted or becomes abnormal [3]. A vast majority of visual impairment/blindness occurring in the form of genetic disease defects is attributed to glaucoma [3]. Glaucoma is an incurable disease of the eye that damages the optic nerve fibre layer of the eye and is usually associated with increased intraocular pressure [2]. Although glaucoma is not curable, treatments such as the use of drugs and surgical operations are used in managing the condition to prevent or delay

permanent vision loss [2].

Glaucoma is a major public health burden and a lead cause of blindness described as irreversible. According to WHO (2021) statistics, the global visual impairment record was pegged at 2.2 billion people. Glaucoma contributes 7.7 million to preventable vision impairment [4]. Based on the Global Burden of Disease Study (GBD, 2021), amongst those aged 50 and above, 4.13 million people and 3.6 million people have suffered from vision impairment and total blindness due to glaucoma. About 67% of glaucoma cases in Europe are said to have remained undetected or undiagnosed [5]. In the UK, the population of people aged 50 years and older with glaucoma is reported to be 4% of this population [6]. In terms of outpatient workload for ophthalmologists and optometrists, about 20% of hospital eye service is attributed to glaucoma [7]. In England alone, hospital eyecare service for

outpatient visitors on account of glaucoma disease has been estimated at over 1 million people [8]. The increase in life expectancy and an ageing UK population portends a rise in the burden of glaucoma [9].

[10], identified late presentation as the main reason for the high numbers of visual impairment and blindness from glaucoma. [10], emphasized increased public knowledge and awareness as a way of tackling late presentations. Interestingly, studies amongst the health workers and professionals population in some countries on their knowledge, attitude, and health-seeking behaviours have provided startling evidence [12]. To date, there has not been any similar study in the UK to provide such evidence; hence, this study investigated the knowledge level, attitude, and health-seeking behaviours of health professionals undergoing postgraduate studies at the University of Sunderland toward blindness prevention.

The knowledge and attitude regarding diseases are known to affect health-seeking behaviour and service uptake [13]. Consequently, a general public that is well informed on glaucoma blinding preventive treatment and care is more likely to seek services. It has been reported that out of the total number of people diagnosed with glaucoma in the UK, only 50% of the total number of people are seeking/receiving treatment, which raises concern about the health-seeking behaviours amongst the UK population towards glaucoma [10]. Evidently, general practitioners are known to influence health behaviour change. Indeed, we cannot also overlook the role other health professionals could play toward health behaviour change [14]. However, their level of awareness and knowledge will determine the impact they make [12], hence, assessing the health professionals undergoing postgraduate study's level of knowledge, attitude, and health-seeking behaviours is a good step toward blindness prevention from glaucoma. Also, knowing how adequately equipped they are with glaucoma information is vital for public health education.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Participants

A quantitative cross-sectional study design was adopted. The study participants for this study were health professionals undergoing postgraduate studies at the Faculty of Health Sciences and Wellbeing, University of Sunderland. An online survey with the Qualtrics software system was conducted through the participants' social media forum. The social media forum used for the participants' recruitment was the Whatsapp and Facebook group pages. In this study, researchers did not conduct face-to-face or self-administered questionnaires because of the COVID-19 pandemic restrictions in place at the period of this research and the closure of the university to mitigate the virus spread. As a result, teaching and learning were virtual thus an online survey could only apply to this study. Participation was voluntary and 104 participants completed the survey.

A Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP) semi-structured questionnaire as utilised by [12], were adapted for this study. The survey instrument was pre-tested to ascertain correctness and appropriateness. Pretesting ensured that content validity was met. To further ascertain and enhance validity, the survey instrument was assessed by a consultant optometrist (eye care specialist) who ensured face validity. A Cronbach Alpha testing to measure the reliability of the study construct gave a high score of 0.844 thus indicating that this study was reliable.

The survey instrument comprised 3 sections:

- Section A: This is made up of questions that seek to obtain information on the demographics of study participants.
- Section B: This comprises questions to determine the awareness and knowledge level of study participants of glaucoma.
- Section C: This is made of questions evaluating the attitude and eye-health-seeking behaviours of study participants towards blindness prevention toward glaucoma.

Sampling method and size

A multistage sampling technique was used for the selection of the study participants. In doing this, the Faculty of Health Sciences and Wellbeing and all the four schools that make up the faculty were conveniently selected. This was followed by the random selection of 26 out of 51 disciplines of the faculty where the participants were picked from. This was done by writing the names of the disciplines on a piece of paper, folded, and placed in a bowl. The bowl was shaken thoroughly and one piece of paper was picked in succession from the bowl until 26 pieces of paper were picked. A total of 104 participants from across the 26 disciplines completed the survey.

The sample size calculation was done using the Formula.

$$n = Z^2pq / (d)^2 \quad (\text{Kish, 1965})$$

Where:

n= desired sample size

z= 1.96 (@ 95%confidence limit)

p= proportion of occurrence: prevalence of glaucoma in Europe= 2.4% i.e. 0.024 [15].

q= proportion of non-occurrence (1-p= 0.915)

d= margin of error (0.03)

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times (0.024) (0.915)}{(0.03)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3.8416 \times 0.024 \times 0.915}{0.0009}$$

$$n = \frac{0.08436}{0.0009}$$

$$n = 93.7 = 94$$

To account for any likely non-responses and losses due to attrition, 10% of n= 94 which is approximately 9 was added to the calculated sample size giving a total sample size (n) of 103 (i.e. 94+9).

Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval to conduct this study was obtained from the University of Sunderland Research Ethics Review Committee with the ethics application number 008005 on 25/11/2020. As participation was voluntary, the Participants' Information Sheet (PIS) where all confidentiality measures were outlined, as well as the consent forms were presented to the participants to obtain informed consent. No personal identifiers such as names were collected during data collection to ensure anonymity. Data collected was stored in a password-protected personal computer of the researchers.

Data Analysis

Data collected from the Qualtrics survey questionnaires were entered into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software program 26.0 for analysis. The analysis performed included descriptive statistics, cross-tabulation, and the Chi-Square test of association. The demographic features and descriptive data were presented in frequency tables and figures. According to evidence on the statistical test, a statistical test can be parametric or non-parametric [16]. A parametric test is conducted when the population data is normally distributed while a non-parametric test is conducted when the data is not normally distributed [17]. A normality test is conducted to determine the distribution of the population data. Both the dependent and independent variables in this study were categorical. This does not meet the requirement of a parametric test hence no test

for normality was required. A parametric test cannot be conducted when the dependent variable is categorical [17]. To compare the distribution of these categorical variables, a non-parametric alternative that is Chi-square test was conducted. The Contingency Coefficient was used to assess the strength of association by looking at the effect size.

RESULTS

Demographic Characteristics of Participants

The demographic profile of study participants (table 1) showed that 44.2% of the participants were males and 55.8% were females. Almost half (45%) of the participants were aged between 28 and 37 years. Most of the participants (70.2%) had no family history of blindness.

Table 1: Frequency Distribution Table

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age range in years		
18 – 27	31	29.8
28 – 37	47	45.2
38 – 47	21	20.2
48 – 57	5	4.8
Gender		
Male	46	44.2
Female	58	55.8
Race		
Africa	38	36.5
Caucasian	34	32.7
Asian	30	28.8
Others	2	1.9
Family history of blindness		
Yes	23	22.1
No	73	70.2
Don't Know	8	7.7
Employment (Currently working within the healthcare system)		
Yes	104	100
No	0	0

Awareness of Glaucoma

Data collected on awareness of glaucoma amongst the participants showed that 79.8% of the participants have heard about glaucoma and 20.2% have not heard of glaucoma. Figure 1 shows that the media was the most common source of information on glaucoma (23.1%) with sources such as health campaigns being the least reported (6.7%).

Figure 1: Information sources on glaucoma awareness amongst postgraduate health professional students of the University of Sunderland.

Knowledge Level and Health-seeking behaviour of Glaucoma

The assessment of the respondents' Knowledge level and health-seeking behaviour is shown in Table 2. The responses to each question by a participant on glaucoma knowledge were awarded scores. Each correct answer was awarded one (1) score whilst an incorrect answer or do not know got a zero (0) score. The scores were summed-up such that 0 – 2 = poor knowledge, 3 – 5 = Fair knowledge, and 6 – 8 = good knowledge. The result from the assessment of knowledge level of glaucoma found that most (44.2%) of the study participants had a fair knowledge of glaucoma whilst 25.0% and 10.6% had poor and good knowledge levels of glaucoma respectively.

All the study participants regardless of awareness level were asked to answer questions on eye health-seeking behaviours. It was found that most (37.5%) of the study participants have never gone for an eye check-up. Although, 40.4% indicated that they would visit an eye doctor if they eventually notice any problem with the use of their eyes, only 28.8% indicated that they will regularly attend doctor's appointments if glaucoma was the diagnosis. Interestingly, the majority (54.8%) of the study participants would refuse surgery as a treatment option for glaucoma.

Table 2: Assessment of Knowledge Level and Eye-Health-seeking Behaviours

Questions/ Response on Glaucoma Knowledge	Frequency (n=104)
What is your understanding of glaucoma?	
High pressure in the eye	34(32.7%)
Damage to the optic nerves associated with high pressure	23(22.1%)
Damage to the retina	15(14.4%)
Coloured haloes and pains in the eye	9(8.7%)
Others	2(1.9%)
Does glaucoma affect both children and adults?	
Yes	31(29.8%)
No	37(35.6%)
Do not know	15(14.4%)
Is glaucoma usually asymptomatic?	
Yes	31(29.8%)
No	39(37.5%)
Do not know	13(12.5%)
Can glaucoma be cured?	
Yes	37(35.6%)
No	36(34.6%)
Do not	10(9.6%)
Is blindness from glaucoma reversible?	
Yes	46(44.2%)
No	25(24.0%)
Do not know	(11.5%)
Blindness from glaucoma is preventable?	
Yes	59(56.7%)
No	19(18.3%)
Do not know	5(4.8%)
Does the risk of glaucoma increase with age?	
Yes	66(63.5%)
No	12(11.5%)
Do not know	5(4.8%)
Can glaucoma be hereditary?	
Yes	29(27.9%)

No	44(42.3%)
Do not Know	10(9.6%)
Questions and answers on Eye-health-seeking behaviours	
When did you last visit an ophthalmologist or optometrist?	
Never	39(37.5%)
3 or more years	26(25.0%)
2 years	14(13.5%)
Do not remember	13(12.5%)
</= 1 year	12(11.5%)
What do you do when you have a problem/trouble with your eye?	
Do nothing	3(2.6%)
Visit the GP/Eye doctor/Optician	40(0.4%)
Visit the pharmacy	16(14.0%)
Self-medication	3(2.6%)
Never had eye problem	35(30.7%)
Others {please specify} Herbs	1(0.9%)
If you were diagnosed with glaucoma, how would you go along with your treatment?	
Regular visit to the GP or eye-care practitioner	30(28.8%)
Regular use of eye drop	27(26.0%)
Not important to regularly visit the hospital or use eye drops	4(3.8%)
Will prefer getting glaucoma surgery done	24(23.1%)
Will only request for eyeglasses	19(18.3%)
If surgery was the only treatment option available, what would you do?	
Will promptly go ahead with the surgery	27(26.0%)
Refuse surgery and continue with eye drops	57(54.8%)
Eye drops and start alternative medicine (Ayurveda or Homeopathy or Yoga)	20(19.2%)
Data presented as frequencies and percent	

Figure 2: Attitude towards glaucoma amongst postgraduate health professional students of the University of Sunderland.

Test for Association

As shown in Table 3, there is a statistically significant relationship between awareness of glaucoma and age, $p=0.025 < 0.05$, though the effect size was moderate as indicated by the Contingency Coefficient of 0.288. The family history of blindness was statistically associated with awareness level $p = 0.037 < 0.05$. Nevertheless, the effect size was minimal with a Contingency Coefficient of 0.244. However, gender was not associated with awareness of glaucoma $p = 0.726 > 0.05$. The test result between Knowledge level and age showed a statistically significant relationship $p= 0.000 < 0.05$ with a large effect size indicated by a Contingency Coefficient of 0.532 thus making age a strong predictor of glaucoma knowledge level. Both gender and family history were not found to be statistically related to glaucoma knowledge level ($p = 0.710$ and 0.194 respectively). The association between age and attitude toward the lifestyle of smoking and excess alcohol intake was found to be positive ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) with a large effect size indicated by a Contingency Coefficient of 0.677. Also, a positive relationship existed between a family history of blindness and attitude toward smoking and excess alcohol intake $p = 0.049 < 0.05$, nevertheless the effect size was moderate (Contingency Coefficient = 0.397).

Attitude towards glaucoma

Five questions assessed the study respondents' attitudes towards glaucoma (Figure 2). The questions were presented on a five-point Likert scale (from strongly agree to strongly disagree). Most (38.6%) of the participants disagreed that anyone could have glaucoma and 42.2% disagreed that lifestyles such as smoking and excess alcohol intake could predispose an individual to glaucoma. In reporting if family members of glaucoma sufferers should be more concerned about having the disease, most (38.6%) of the participants disagreed. In comparing glaucoma with other eye diseases in terms of priority to treatment, the majority (39.8%) of the respondents agreed that it is a priority disease. When compared to other threatening body diseases other than eye diseases, 41.0% disagreed that it is a priority disease. Overall, the majority of the answers indicated by the respondents are largely contentious which could suggest a negative attitude towards glaucoma.

Table 3: Relationship between Socio-demographic and Awareness, Knowledge level, and Lifestyle Attitude toward Glaucoma

Awareness of Glaucoma						
Variable	Heard (%)	Not Heard (%)	Total	X ²	P value	Contingency Coefficient
Age Range				9.375	0.025	0.288
18-27	29(93.5%)	2(6.5%)	31(100.0%)			
28-37	36(76.6%)	11(23.4%)	47(100.0%)			
38-47	13(61.9%)	9(38.1%)	21(100.0%)			
48-57	5(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	5(100.0%)			
Total	83(79.8%)	21(20.2%)	104(100.0%)			
Gender				0.122	0.726	0.034
Male	36(78.3%)	10(21.7%)	46(100%)			
Female	47(81.0%)	11(19.0%)	58(100%)			
Total	83(79.8%)	21(20.2%)	104(100%)			
Family History of Blindness				6.602	0.037	0.244
Yes	14(60.9%)	9(39.1%)	23(100%)			
No	62(84.9%)	11(15.1%)	73(100%)			
Don't Know	7(87.5%)	1(12.5%)	8(100%)			
Total	83(79.8%)	21(20.2%)	104(100%)			

Knowledge level of Glaucoma							
	Poor Knowledge	Fair Knowledge	Good Knowledge	Total	X ²	P-value	Contingency Coefficient
Age Range					32.758	0.000	0.532
18-27	1(3.2%)	21(67.7%)	9(29.0%)	31(100.0%)			
28-37	24(53.3%)	21(46.7%)	0(0.0%)	45(100.0%)			
38-47	0(0.0%)	2(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	2(100.0%)			
48-57	1(20.0%)	2(40.0%)	2(40.0%)	5(100.0%)			
Total	26(31.3%)	46(55.4%)	11(13.3%)	83(100.0%)			
Gender					0.686	0.710	0.091
Male	11(27.5%)	24(60.0%)	5(12.5%)	40(100.0%)			
Female	15(34.9%)	22(51.2%)	6(14.0%)	43(100.0%)			
Total	26(31.3%)	46(55.4%)	11(13.3%)	83(100.0%)			
Family History of Blindness					2.323	0.194	0.261
Yes	2(13.3%)	10(66.7%)	3(20.0%)	15(100.0%)			
No	24(38.1%)	32(50.8%)	7(11.1%)	63(100.0%)			
Don't Know	0(0.0%)	4(80.0%)	12(0.0%)	5(100.0%)			
Total	26(31.3%)	46(55.4%)	11(13.3%)	83(100.0%)			

Do you think lifestyle attitude (smoking and excess alcohol intake) puts an individual at risk of glaucoma?									
	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Total	X ²	P-Value	Contingency Coefficient

Age Range							70.106	0.000	0.677
18-27	0(0.00%)	0(0.0%)	2(6.5%)	29(93.5%)	0(0.0%)	31(100%)			
28-37	6(13.3%)	14(31.0%)	17(37.8%)	2(4.4%)	6(13.3%)	45(100%)			
38-47	0(0.00%)	0(0.0%)	2(100.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	2(100%)			
48-57	0(0.00%)	0(0.0%)	1(20.0%)	48(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	5(100%)			
Total	6(7.2%)	14(16.9%)	22(26.5%)	35(42.2%)	6(7.2%)	83(100%)			
Family History of Blindness							15.546	0.049	0.397
Yes	0(0.0%)	5(33.3%)	3(20.0%)	74(6.7%)	0(0.0%)	15(100%)			
No	6(9.5%)	8(12.7%)	19(30.2%)	26(41.3%)	4(6.3%)	63(100%)			
Don't Know	0(0.0%)	12(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	24(0.0%)	2(40.0%)	5(100%)			
Total	6(7.2%)	14(16.9%)	22(26.5%)	35(42.2%)	6(7.2%)	83(100%)			

DISCUSSION

Summary of Findings

This quantitative study is the first of its kind in the UK that examined the knowledge, attitude, and health-seeking behaviours of health professionals towards blindness prevention from glaucoma. Awareness of glaucoma amongst the health professionals was high in this study, however, the knowledge level regarding the understanding of glaucoma was fair. The health professionals' attitude towards glaucoma was unencouraging which was evident in the poor eye-health-seeking behaviour of the professionals especially to undergo routine eye checks to ascertain glaucoma status. This study established that important factors such as age and family history of blindness were notable predictors of glaucoma awareness and knowledge level (Family history was not found to predict knowledge level) as well as attitude towards glaucoma amongst health professionals similar to that reported in various general population study [18-20].

Alternative Explanation of Findings

As professionals in healthcare, it is very understandable that at some point during training or in practice, the participants in our study might have heard of glaucoma which explains the high awareness. Educational and employment status have been linked to glaucoma awareness [11]. Nevertheless, there may be reasons as to why their knowledge and understanding of glaucoma disease appear to be moderate. One of such could be traced to professional specialisation. [14], reported that amongst student health professionals, only those in the field of optometry and ophthalmology adequately understood the issues around glaucoma. According to Achigbu and [21], study, non-ophthalmic doctors demonstrated some measure of deficiency in glaucoma information including test examination and management procedures. They were also found to be more unlikely to seek routine eye check-ups. This explains the effect of specialisation on glaucoma knowledge level, attitude, and eye-health-seeking behaviour as demonstrated in our study where the health professionals that cut across all spheres of health practice had a fair knowledge of glaucoma, and a relatively poor attitude. and health-seeking behaviour.

Another reason that explains fair knowledge of glaucoma could also be due to the structure of the healthcare system in the UK where eyecare services are mainly operated as a private practice and interaction with the general health set-up seem to occur at a distance. As such only specialists specifically trained for eyecare management in whatever capacity as an ophthalmic nurse, optometrist or ophthalmologist can boast of competency in the knowledge and understanding of glaucoma whereas other health

professionals are deprived of that.

Furthermore, several studies have highlighted the effect of perception (perceived susceptibility, severity, and benefit) as an underlying factor in knowledge level, attitude, and health behaviour in diverse health diseases and problems [22, 23]. Perhaps, the participants in our study just like it was found in some patient-based and population-based studies [24, 25], might not perceive glaucoma as an ocular and health emergency as such had a significant impact on their knowledge level, attitude, and eye-health-seeking behaviour towards blindness prevention from glaucoma.

Also, there is a huge focus on patients when dealing with glaucoma education [25]. This strategy in itself appears to be reactive. Preventive strategies would be a more effective strategy especially when one considers the phenomenon of late presentation; fingered at the root of eventual blindness due to glaucoma. Propagating awareness and health education is a preventive strategy usually driven by health professionals and trained specialists. The evidence of less utilisation of preventive strategy is seen in moderate knowledge level, poor attitude, and eye-health seeking amongst health professionals who have been earmarked as agents of health behaviour change that command public trust to influence health behaviour. Some of the point raised here offers an alternative explanation of the aspect of our study finding herein.

Comparing Findings with existing Literature

Population-based and patient-based studies on glaucoma are extensive and have dominated the global literature on glaucoma study when compared with the glaucoma study focus on health professionals. This is also the case in the UK where this study presented evidence on the aspect of knowledge level, attitude, and health-seeking behaviour amongst health professionals towards glaucoma blindness prevention that was hitherto unknown. A study by [12], had previously explored this glaucoma study focus amongst the same population and there are several elements of our study findings that resonate with their own findings.

The awareness level amongst the health professionals in our study was high (79.8%) similar to the finding by Adegbehingbe and Bisiriyu (2008) and [12], with 95.1% and 100.0% respectively. It is also surprising that the participants in these two studies conducted in two different developing countries (Nigeria and India respectively) had a comparable higher glaucoma awareness level than our study in the UK even though the UK as a developed nation has better health status and social determinants of health. Perhaps, the higher prevalence of glaucoma and blindness in those

regions of the world makes for a greater awareness level of the disease even amongst health professionals. [10], had found a high level of glaucoma awareness amongst the UK population, same as [26]. The manner in which awareness was interpreted in this study was on the basis of “having heard of glaucoma” similar to the design used in studies by [20, 27].

In our study, the media was found to be the main (23.1%) source of information on glaucoma awareness similar to what [10, 28], reported in their study. This is a demonstration of the power of the media to inform and communicate disease awareness amongst other things. It can therefore be effectively utilised as a tool to disseminate information and engage the general public on matters of health education and health improvement to avoid preventable diseases.

Amongst the health professionals who were aware of glaucoma and examined to ascertain their knowledge level of glaucoma, 44.2% (which represents the highest percentage) of them were found to possess a fair knowledge level of glaucoma. This finding is consistent with [12], study interestingly reported that out of every 1 in 4 GP and nurses, adequate knowledge of glaucoma is lacking and only ophthalmologists and optometrists possessed sufficient and robust knowledge of glaucoma. This gap could be playing out in the poor glaucoma knowledge level within the general population which has been reported in several other studies [29, 30]. This is because to reduce the incidences of blindness due to glaucoma, health professionals as agents of health behaviour are key thus their knowledge level of glaucoma is a paramount requirement.

Adegbhingbe and Bisiriyu demonstrated that disease knowledge is linked to attitude and self-care practices towards the disease. The study reported that higher knowledge of the glaucoma disease translated to a positive outlook with regard to attitude and self-care practices to prevent the blinding effect of glaucoma. Our study found that the attitude of health professionals towards glaucoma prevention and management was relatively poor which supports the finding of Adegbhingbe and Bisiriyu. The evidence on the attitude of our study participants toward glaucoma could be a reflection of their poor eye-health-seeking behaviour. Our study found that only a combined 50% of the health professionals had visited an eyecare specialist for a thorough eye examination or any form of eyecare services within the last 1 year, 2 years, 3 years, or more. About 37.5% of the participants have never done vision screening. Even with proximity to health facilities, they are yet to know their eye-health status. Perhaps, the uptake and utilisation of eye care services is not entirely a function of the accessibility effect just as [21], had reported in their study.

Our study found some important predictors of awareness and knowledge level as well as attitude toward glaucoma blindness prevention to include age and family history of blindness. Age and family history were associated with glaucoma awareness whereas age was the only positive predictor of knowledge level. Furthermore, age and family history of blindness was found to be a predictive factor of attitude of health professionals toward the lifestyle of smoking and alcoholism which has been noted in the literature as a risk factor that impacts the glaucoma blinding effect [2]. Our study, therefore, lends support to. [18, 20, 29], studies. The chances of visiting an eye specialist for eye examination increase with age especially when eye conditions like presbyopia (age-related refractive condition) set in which could indirectly rob off on awareness of glaucoma. Also, people that have a family member who is blind or have a family history of blindness could most likely be aware of glaucoma since glaucoma is one of the leading blinding diseases and they may be more interested in knowing their eye-health status. It appears that the older population and those with a family history of blindness in our sample were more likely to be more knowledgeable about glaucoma and would be more disposed to show a positive attitude toward adopting good health-seeking behaviour. This supports [29], position that increasing age and family history of blindness

improve one's attitude to glaucoma and as such could translate to positive eye health-seeking behaviour [31-39].

Relevance of Research to Practice and Policy

Research in the UK around this topic area remains hugely uninterrogated. Infact the first UK study on glaucoma public awareness and knowledge was conducted in 2010 [10]. Our study findings have practical implications. Society would be uninformed if glaucoma knowledge insufficiency is prevalent amongst health professionals who are agents of health behaviour change. Implicitly, behaviours that facilitates raising incidences of blindness would remain persistent within the general population.

Our research has provided evidence of the level of knowledge, attitude and health-seeking behaviours of health professionals towards blindness prevention from glaucoma thus contributing knowledge to the body of literature and further setting the tone for additional research on this topic. Evidence from this study has provided a strong argument on the need for informational programmes such as seminars and glaucoma workshops amongst others for health professionals especially nurses who are usually the first point-contact professionals. These informational programmes can be utilised by public health authorities, policymakers, and concerned stakeholders in health to equip health professionals properly with the right glaucoma information for a better outcome in the health education of the public towards reducing and preventing blindness.

Furthermore, based on our findings, age and family of blindness could be likened as two important epidemiological risk factors for prioritisation in public health planning and campaigns toward glaucoma blindness prevention. In addition, on the basis of our findings on the health-seeking behaviours of health professionals who are apparently domesticated within health facilities, it is therefore recommended that further research is explored to understand the underlying pathway between accessibility and service uptake of glaucoma care.

Limitations

This study suffered some drawbacks. Firstly, the use of postgraduate health professionals from one university and the sample size of 104 may be considered small for a typical quantitative study, thus limiting the extent to which this study can be generalised to the entire population. Secondly, the self-reported questionnaire utilised could have introduced response bias (social desirability bias) and recall bias as some of the questions were asked in retrospect. To minimize this, the researcher patterned the answers to the questions to reduce the recall period. Finally, this study suffered from a lack of temporality in the use of cross-sectional design as such no causal inferences could be inferred rather associations between variables were established.

CONCLUSION

Despite efforts to reduce the blinding effect of glaucoma, the evidence available showed that much is yet to be achieved as it remains one of the leading causes of visual impairment globally and in the UK. The discovery through the literature on conflicting research within the UK on the glaucoma knowledge level, and negative attitude and eye-health-seeking behaviour on the part of those needing treatment set this study in motion. The evidence from this study finding proved that it would be wrong to assume that all health professionals are sufficiently knowledgeable about glaucoma. Therefore, how well they will function as agents of health behaviour change becomes concerning and questionable. Health professionals need to have good knowledge of glaucoma. This will help them to also adopt good eye-health-seeking behaviour and in turn, provide appropriate advice and support to the public when their opinion is sought. The media had the greatest impact on the awareness of the postgraduate health professionals; hence it could be used as an effective tool to educate the general

population during public health education and campaigns. Importantly, there is a need for the continuous professional education of health professionals with the targeted objective of blindness prevention.

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Authors Contributions

The conceptualisation and the design of the study were collaboratively done by both authors – Emmanuel Tochukwu Anyaehie (ETA) and Vivian Chinonso Osuchukwu (VCO). Both authors agreed on taking personal responsibility for their contributions thus maintaining a high level of integrity throughout this work. ETA coined the title; the phrasing and screening of the title were conducted by VCO whilst ETA reviewed related literature to this work and drafted the abstract. The instrument of data collection was adapted by ETA and VCO offered face validity. Primary data collection was carried out by ETA. Analysis of data was by ETA with VCO also contributing substantially. ETA drafted the manuscript which was revised by VCO. The manuscript publication was approved by both authors.

Conflicting Interest

The authors do hereby declare no competing interest whether financial or otherwise.

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